

Antiproliferative Activity and Structure-Activity Relationships of Novel Au(III)-Thiosemicarbazone Complexes: An Evaluation of the PPP4 Series

Haoyu (Jason) Liu, Dr. Mahendiran Dharmasivam, Dr. Busra Kaya, and Professor Des Richardson
s5441118 Griffith University

ABSTRACT: The development of metal-based anticancer agents has expanded beyond platinum drugs such as cisplatin, which primarily target DNA through covalent binding following intracellular aquation. While effective, Cisplatin is limited by severe toxicities like nephrotoxicity and neurotoxicity and the emergence of multidrug resistance (MDR). In contrast, thiosemicarbazones have shown to exert cytotoxicity through a “double-punch” mechanism involving intracellular iron sequestration and the generation of cytotoxic reactive oxygen species (ROS). This paper evaluates the antiproliferative capability of two sixth-generation thiosemicarbazone ligands, (E)-3-phenyl-1-(pyridine-2-yl)prop-2-en-1-one-morpholine-1-thiosemicarbazone (PPP4MT) and the pyrrolidine-substituted analogue, (E)-3-phenyl-1-(pyridine-2-yl)prop-2-en-1-one-pyrrolidine-1-thiosemicarbazone (PPP4PyrT), together with the corresponding Au(III) complexes $[\text{Au}(\text{PPP4MT})\text{Cl}]^+$ and $[\text{Au}(\text{PPP4PyrT})\text{Cl}]^+$. Au(III) was incorporated because it is a d8 metal centre that typically adopts square-planar geometry (analogous to Pt(II)), potentially providing greater complex stability while retaining thiosemicarbazone-driven biological targeting. The compounds were assessed against the iron-dependent MDA-MB-231 Triple-Negative Breast Cancer (TNBC) cell using a 72h MTT cellular viability assay, with data collected using their half-maximal inhibitory concentrations, IC_{50} values. The results showed that free ligand PPP4MT was the most potent agent. While coordination to Au(III) resulted in chemically stable square-planar complexes, leading to a reduction in antiproliferative potency for both ligands compared to free ligands. Physicochemical properties may contribute to differences in potency (e.g., permeability/solubility), but they do not fully explain the observed activity, indicating mechanistic factors also play a key role. Analysis also revealed that Au(III) coordination increased molecular weight and lipophilicity, which may reduce alignment with common drug-likeness guides. These findings demonstrate Au(III) modifies structure-activity relationships in the PPP4HAT ligand series, which therefore warrants further mechanistic validation using assays which directly measure intracellular metal handling and oxidation species.

INTRODUCTION

Cancer is one of the leading causes of death worldwide, accounting for one in six deaths (Bray et al., 2024). In Australia, breast cancer remains the most common diagnosis among women, with approximately 20,000 new cases annually (AIHW, 2023). While targeted therapies have revolutionised treatment for some types of cancers, cytotoxic chemotherapy remains the main method of therapy for treating malignancies like TNBC (Foulkes et al., 2010). TNBC is characterised by the lack of Estrogen Receptor (ER), Progesterone Receptor (PR) and Human Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor 2 (HER2); its absence of specific molecular targets makes it notoriously difficult to treat (Upadhyay, 2020). As a consequence, there are two main limiting barriers to the efficacy of conventional chemotherapeutic agents: non-selective toxicity towards healthy proliferating tissues, and rapid Multi-Drug Resistance (MDR) through mechanisms like the overexpression of P-glycoprotein efflux pump (Holohan et al., 2013; Gottesman et al., 2002). This therefore necessitates urgent development of novel agents that operate via

mechanisms distinct from classical DNA-alkylating chemotherapies (Hanahan & Weinberg, 2011).

Inorganic medicinal chemistry was founded on the basis of Cisplatin discovery (cis-diamminedichloroplatinum(II)). As a neutral, square-planar prodrug, Cisplatin undergoes aquation in the cell, binding covalently to DNA purine bases. This forms crosslinks that inhibit replication, triggering apoptosis (Johnstone et al., 2016). Critically, this mechanism is primarily DNA-centric and involves minimal redox activity. The Pt(II) centre is kinetically stable, preventing redox cycling. While this is effective, this mechanism is commonly associated with severe dose-limiting nephrotoxicity and neurotoxicity. Resistance can arise through reduced drug accumulation (e.g., altered influx/efflux transport) and detoxification by intracellular thiols (e.g., glutathione/metallothioneins), which limits platinum reaching DNA. These limitations highlight the need for the development of non-platinum metallodrugs, which bypass these resistance pathways.

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Thiosemicarbazones represent a part of the Schiff class of ligands, demonstrating strong anticancer activity potential. Unlike Cisplatin, they function through a double-punch mechanism (Richardson et al., 2006), as shown in Figure 1. Punch 1 involves iron depletion in which rapidly dividing cancer cells have an elevated requirement for iron, which is driven by the upregulation of Transferrin Receptor 1 (TfR1) (Lane et al., 2014; Whitnall et al., 2006) and Ribonucleotide Reductase (RR). Thiosemicarbazones act as membrane-permeable chelators, removing intracellular iron from RR, an iron-dependent rate-limiting enzyme in DNA synthesis; this induces a lack of iron and terminates the cell cycle at the G1/S position (Lane et al., 2014; Whitnall et al., 2006). Punch 2 involves redox recycling in which the binding to intracellular iron or copper can generate redox-active complexes that catalyse ROS formation. In the presence of physiological reductants, the complex cycles between Fe(II) and Fe(III). Consequently, this catalyses the reduction of molecular oxygen to generate cytotoxic ROS via Fenton chemistry (Stacy et al., 2016). The redox cycling of the iron complex can be described by the equations:

The generated hydroxyl radicals (HO·) can contribute to oxidative stress and damage to redox-sensitive cellular compartments (e.g., lysosomes/mitochondria), promoting cell death.

Figure 1. Schematic overview of the proposed “double-punch” mechanism of thiosemicarbazones, including iron sequestration and redox cycling that can elevate ROS, alongside key downstream signalling effects reported for PPP-series ligands. Adapted from Dharmasivam et al. (2023).

The specific mechanism of targeting lysosomes and mitochondria to promote cell death is shown in Figure 2, with Dp44mT shown to form redox-active Cu-Dp44mT complexes, which then generates ROS inducing lysosomal membrane permeabilisation.

Figure 2. Schematic overview of Dp44mT lysosomal membrane permeabilisation (LMP). Adapted from Dharmasivam et al. (2023).

Clinical progression of thiosemicarbazones has evolved through many iterations. First-generation Dp44mT possessed nanomolar potency, but caused cardiac fibrosis due to non-selective ROS generation (Lovejoy et al., 2012). Second-generation DpC improved cardiac safety, but the oxidation of oxyhemoglobin (Fe^{2+}) to methemoglobin (Fe^{3+}) resulted in hypoxia and muscle pain, linked to clinical adverse effects (Quach et al., 2012; Stefani et al., 2013).

Dharmasivam et al. (2023) developed the third-generation (E)-3-phenyl-1-(pyridine-2-yl)prop-2-en-1-one-4,4-dimethyl-3-thiosemicarbazone (PPP44mT) series to tune redox properties while retaining anti-tumour activity and minimising heme-centre oxidation. This allowed for a redox potential that maintained anti-tumor properties, while preventing oxidation of hemoglobin iron (Dharmasivam et al., 2023; Dharmasivam et al., 2025). Therefore, the need to develop ligands that do not oxidise blood proteins underpins the selection of PPP44mT for this study.

Incorporating Gold(III) into thiosemicarbazone is a hybrid strategy. Gold(III) possesses a d^8 electronic configuration. This makes it isoelectronic and isostructural with Pt(II), forming stable square-planar complexes (Bernhardt, 2011). It is hypothesised that strong Gold(III) coordination may stabilise the ligand, which prevents premature metabolism prior to reaching the tumour. Moreover, gold complexes target thioredoxin reductase (TrxR), a selenocysteine-containing enzyme critical for cellular redox balance (Berners-Price & Filipovska, 2011). This ensures target diversification.

Therefore, this study evaluates the structure-activity relationships (SAR) of two novel sixth-generation ligands, PPP44mT (methyl substitution) and PPP44PyrT (pyrrolidine substituted), and determines the effect of Gold(III) coordination on biological activity.

Figure 3. Chemical structures of the thiosemicarbazone ligands and their corresponding Au(III) complexes examined in this study. Shown are (A) the sixth-generation thiosemicarbazone ligand PPP4MT and (B) its gold(III) complex [Au(PPP4MT)Cl]⁺, together with (C) the pyrrolidine-substituted analogue PPP4PyrT and (D) its corresponding gold(III) complex [Au(PPP4PyrT)Cl]⁺. In the Au(III) complexes, gold is coordinated by the tridentate thiosemicarbazone *N,N,S* donor set, with a terminal chloride ligand completing the coordination sphere.

Chemical Structures and Design of the Thiosemicarbazone Ligands and Their Au(III) Complexes

The chemical structures of the sixth-generation thiosemicarbazone ligands examined in this study, together with their corresponding gold(III) complexes, are shown in Figure 3. The compounds investigated include the parent thiosemicarbazone ligand PPP4MT and a structurally related pyrrolidine-substituted analogue, PPP4PyrT. To

assess the influence of metal coordination on biological activity, each ligand was also examined in its Au(III)-coordinated form, namely [Au(PPP4MT)Cl]⁺ and [Au(PPP4PyrT)Cl]⁺ (Figure 3).

Both ligands contain the characteristic thiosemicarbazone framework, which is known to coordinate metal ions through a tridentate *N,N,S* donor set (Figure 3).

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12

	Media
	Drug solution

Figure 5. Schematic diagram of cell plate following thiosemicarbazone addition, prior to serial dilution process

By multi-channel pipetting, serial dilution was performed, placing 125 μ L of thiosemicarbazones from Column 11 into Column 10. The mixture was thoroughly homogenised by pipetting. Successively, 125 μ L was extracted from the previous row and placed into the next adjacent row in decreasing consecutive row order. For example, Column 10 now contained 125 μ L from Column 11 in solution, and 125 μ L of media placed previously, totalling 250 μ L. This causes each drug concentration to halve as the serial dilution proceeds (Figure 6). In Column 2, the 125 μ L was discarded now that all columns contained 125 μ L.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12

	Media
	Drug solution - serial dilution increasing concentration (opacity) →

Figure 6. Schematic diagram of serial dilution process of thiosemicarbazones in treatment plate.

To increase drug miscibility for transportation into cell plate, plain media was added on top of the wells of the treatment plate. 125 μ L of media was pipetted into

Column 12 first, and then into Column 1, then in ascending consecutive row number order from Column 2 to 11. The purpose of conducting this in reverse to serial dilution order is to reduce the error, where contamination of lower concentrations into higher concentration wells has a lesser impact on results than the converse. Next, the mixture in the treatment plate was placed into the cell plates. 100 μ L from each well in the treatment plate was transferred into the same position in the cell plate. This plate was then incubated for 72 hours prior to data reading and analysis.

A MTT solution was then prepared where 20 μ L of MTT solution (5mg/mL solution in PBS) was added to each well and incubated for 2 hours. The action of the mitochondrial oxidoreductase enzyme facilitates the reduction of yellow MTT tetrazolium salts to purple formazan crystals through the MTT assay mechanism (Mosmann, 1983). As the reduction process requires mitochondrial function and metabolic activity, this can only be performed on viable, live cells. MTT solution and media was then removed from the plates using pipettes, and 100 μ L of DMSO was added to each well to solubilise the violet formazan crystals. The plates were undisturbed for 5 minutes, as formazan crystals are insoluble in media, and the polarity of DMSO as an organic solvent provides a homogenous solution that allows for accurate absorbance measurements (Carmichael et al., 1987). Absorbance was then measured at 570nm using a Victor3 microplate reader. Calculations were then made to determine cell viability by measuring the absorbance of each well at 570nm. Cell viability was calculated by the formula:

$$\text{cell viability (\%)} = \frac{\text{absorbance in desired well (A570)}}{\text{absorbance of control column (A570)}}$$

A standard curve was then plotted at varying concentrations and proliferation as a percentage of control (Figure 7) for all measured compounds.

RESULTS

Effects of the Ligands and Au(III) Complexes on Breast Cancer Cell Viability

The antiproliferative activity of PPP4MT, PPP4PyrT, and their corresponding Au(III) complexes was evaluated using an MTT cell viability assay in MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cells following 72 h of drug exposure. The resulting concentration–response curves are shown in Figure 7. The MTT assay measures cellular metabolic activity and is commonly used as an indicator of viable, proliferating cells, with reduced absorbance corresponding to decreased cell viability.

Figure 7. Concentration–response curves showing the effects of the sixth-generation thiosemicarbazone ligands PPP4MT and PPP4PyrT and their corresponding Au(III) complexes ($[\text{Au}(\text{PPP4MT})\text{Cl}]^+$ and $[\text{Au}(\text{PPP4PyrT})\text{Cl}]^+$) on MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cell viability following 72 h exposure. Cells were treated with increasing concentrations of each compound (as indicated in the figure), and viability was determined using the MTT assay. Data are presented as mean \pm SD from three independent experiments.

As illustrated in Figure 7, all compounds produced concentration-dependent reductions in cell viability, although the extent and potency of these effects varied significantly between compounds. The free ligand PPP4MT demonstrated strong antiproliferative activity, with a pronounced decrease in cell viability observed at low micromolar to sub-micromolar concentrations. The steep slope of the concentration–response curve indicates that relatively small increases in concentration result in substantial reductions in cell viability, consistent with a highly potent antiproliferative agent.

PPP4PyrT also inhibited cell viability in a concentration-dependent manner; however, its concentration–response curve was shifted to the right relative to PPP4MT (Figure 7). This shift indicates reduced potency, as higher concentrations of PPP4PyrT were required to achieve similar levels of growth inhibition. This observation suggests that pyrrolidine substitution within the thiosemicarbazone scaffold alters biological activity, potentially by influencing cellular uptake, intracellular distribution, or interactions with molecular targets.

Coordination to Au(III) affected the concentration–response behaviour of both ligands. The Au(III) complex $[\text{Au}(\text{PPP4MT})\text{Cl}]^+$ retained substantial antiproliferative activity but showed a modest rightward shift in the concentration–response curve compared with the free ligand, indicating reduced potency (Figure 7). A similar trend was observed for PPP4PyrT, with $[\text{Au}(\text{PPP4PyrT})\text{Cl}]^+$ displaying further reduced activity relative to the free ligand. These data demonstrate that gold coordination

modifies, but does not inhibit the antiproliferative effects of this ligand series (Figure 7).

Table 1. Antiproliferative activity of the sixth-generation thiosemicarbazone ligands PPP4MT and PPP4PyrT and their corresponding Au(III) complexes ($[\text{Au}(\text{PPP4MT})\text{Cl}]^+$ and $[\text{Au}(\text{PPP4PyrT})\text{Cl}]^+$) against MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cells. IC_{50} values (μM) were determined from three independent experiments and are reported as mean \pm SD.

Compounds	IC_{50} (μM)
PPP4MT	0.02 ± 0.01
$[\text{Au}(\text{PPP4MT})\text{Cl}]^+$	0.05 ± 0.01
PPP4PyrT	0.09 ± 0.02
$[\text{Au}(\text{PPP4PyrT})\text{Cl}]^+$	0.14 ± 0.01

Quantitative Antiproliferative Potency Determined by IC_{50} Analysis

To quantitatively compare antiproliferative potency, IC_{50} values were calculated from the concentration–response curves and are summarised in Table 1. The IC_{50} value represents the concentration of compound required to reduce cell viability by 50 percent and is a widely accepted metric for comparing drug potency.

PPP4MT exhibited the highest potency among the compounds tested, with an IC_{50} value of 0.02 ± 0.01 μM . This extremely low IC_{50} value confirms the strong antiproliferative activity observed in the MTT assay and indicates that PPP4MT is highly effective at

inhibiting MDA-MB-231 cell growth. Upon coordination to Au(III), the potency of PPP4MT decreased modestly, with $[\text{Au}(\text{PPP4MT})\text{Cl}]^+$ displaying an IC_{50} value of $0.05 \pm 0.01 \mu\text{M}$ (Table 1). Although this represents a reduction in potency of approximately two- to three-fold, the Au(III) complex remains highly active within the sub-micromolar range.

PPP4PyrT exhibited lower potency than PPP4MT, with an IC_{50} value of $0.09 \pm 0.02 \mu\text{M}$. This reduction in activity relative to PPP4MT is consistent with the right-shifted concentration–response curve observed in Figure 7 and highlights the sensitivity of biological activity to structural modification within this ligand series. Coordination of PPP4PyrT to Au(III) further reduced potency, with $[\text{Au}(\text{PPP4PyrT})\text{Cl}]^+$ displaying an IC_{50} value of $0.14 \pm 0.01 \mu\text{M}$ (Table 1). Together, these data demonstrate that both ligand structure and metal coordination play important roles in determining antiproliferative potency.

DISCUSSION

The comparison between PPP4MT and PPP4PyrT provides critical SAR insight. PPP4MT exhibited much greater potency (IC_{50} : $0.02 \mu\text{M}$) compared to PPP4PyrT (IC_{50} : $0.09 \mu\text{M}$). The pyrrolidine substituent may alter potency by changing physicochemical properties (e.g., basicity, polarity, and steric profile), which can affect cellular uptake and intracellular distribution, and potentially the efficiency of engaging iron-dependent targets. Moreover, the cyclic secondary amine has different electronic inductive effects compared to linear alkyl amines in PPP4MT, which could alter the electron density at the metal-binding domain.

This aligns with SAR studies by Dharmasivam et al. (2023) demonstrating that potency can be adjusted by small N4-terminus modifications without completely removing it.

A key finding is that Au(III) coordination reduced antiproliferative potency. This contrasts with Copper(II) complexes, in which coordination usually enhances cytotoxicity via redox cycling (Dharmasivam et al., 2024).

This can be understood through two mechanisms. Firstly, copper is redox-reactive, cycling between Cu(I) and Cu(II); this catalyses ROS production. Comparatively, Au(III) is isoelectronic to Pt(II), resulting in inert square-planar complexes forming. Secondly, the data suggests a plausible explanation is that Au(III) coordination reduces the ability of the scaffold to access iron-dependent pathways (e.g., iron binding/transmetalation), thereby attenuating components of the classical ‘double-punch’ mechanism. This requires direct validation (e.g., iron mobilisation/uptake assays, ROS readouts, and metal-uptake measurements). The ligand’s iron-binding capacity is then neutralised.

However, the Au(III) complexes are active in the sub-micromolar range (Table 1), indicating that coordination attenuates and does not inhibit biological activity, which may be through a shift toward alternative gold-associated targets like TrxR. Gold compounds bind to selenocysteine active sites of TrxR with high affinity (Berners-Price & Filipovska, 2011). As a consequence, cytotoxicity may arise due to TrxR inhibition rather than iron depletion, representing a shifting molecular target. This explains the higher IC_{50} values, in which this mechanism switch is less efficient than the multi-target free ligand.

This reduction in potency is further explained by Lipinski’s Rule of 5 in Table 2 (Lipinski et al., 2001).

Table 2. Calculated physicochemical properties of the sixth-generation thiosemicarbazone ligands PPP4MT and PPP4PyrT and their corresponding Au(III) complexes ($[\text{Au}(\text{PPP4MT})\text{Cl}]^+$ and $[\text{Au}(\text{PPP4PyrT})\text{Cl}]^+$). Reported parameters include molecular weight (M.W.), calculated log P ($\log P_{\text{calc}}$), hydrogen-bond acceptors (HBA), hydrogen-bond donors (HBD), number of rotatable bonds, and topological polar surface area (TPSA). The final row lists commonly accepted guideline values for drug-like small molecules. All compounds fall within recommended limits for HBA, HBD, rotatable bonds, and TPSA, while the Au(III) complexes exceed the preferred molecular-weight threshold.

Compounds	M.W.	log <i>P</i> (calc.)	HBA (N + O)	HBD (NH + OH)	Rot. bonds	TPSA (Å ²)
PPP4MT	352.46	3.07	5	1	6	49.76
$[\text{Au}(\text{PPP4MT})\text{Cl}]^+$	583.88	3.93	5	0	3	31.73
PPP4PyrT	336.46	3.62	4	1	6	40.52
$[\text{Au}(\text{PPP4PyrT})\text{Cl}]^+$	567.88	4.49	4	0	3	22.49
Required	< 500	< 5	< 10	< 5	< 10	< 140

Physicochemical Properties and Their Relationship to Biological Activity

The calculated physicochemical properties of the ligands and their Au(III) complexes are presented in Table 2. These parameters provide insight into factors that influence drug-like behaviour, including molecular weight, lipophilicity, polarity, hydrogen-bonding capacity, and molecular flexibility, all of which can affect cellular uptake and intracellular activity.

Both free ligands, PPP4MT and PPP4PyrT, fall within commonly used drug-likeness guidelines (e.g., Lipinski-style thresholds) for drug-like small molecules. Their molecular weights are below 500 Da, calculated $\log P_{calc}$ values are below 5, and their hydrogen-bond donor and acceptor counts, rotatable bond numbers, and topological polar surface area (TPSA) values are all within recommended limits (Table 2). These properties suggest a balance between lipophilicity and polarity that may support membrane permeability and intracellular access, which is consistent with the observed antiproliferative activity.

Coordination to Au(III) increased molecular weight for both complexes, exceeding the commonly cited 500 Da guideline for oral small molecules (Table 2). In addition, Au(III) coordination increased lipophilicity and reduced TPSA and hydrogen-bond donor capacity. While increased lipophilicity can enhance membrane association, the accompanying increase in size and reduction in polarity may negatively influence solubility or intracellular distribution. Importantly, despite similar physicochemical trends for both Au(III) complexes, their biological activities differ from those of the free ligands, indicating that physicochemical parameters alone cannot fully explain antiproliferative potency.

In summary, this dataset demonstrates that PPP4MT is the most potent compound examined, displaying strong antiproliferative activity against MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cells. Structural modification to give PPP4PyrT results in reduced potency, highlighting a clear structure–activity relationship within this ligand series. Coordination to Au(III) attenuates activity for both ligands but does not eliminate antiproliferative effects, indicating that metal coordination alters the efficiency rather than the presence of biological activity.

These findings underscore the importance of rational ligand design and careful evaluation of metal coordination effects in the development of metal-based anticancer agents.

A limitation of this study is that it relies on the MTT assay which measures metabolic activity rather than direct cell death. Future validation could involve use of DCFDA ROS assays to quantify whether Au(III) complexes generate less ROS compared to free ligands. Furthermore, ICP-MS could be used to quantify intracellular gold accumulation, alongside assays that assess effects on cellular iron pools; this

would clarify whether reduced potency is associated with reduced cellular accumulation and/or altered intracellular speciation (e.g., limited ligand release/metal exchange).

CONCLUSIONS

Therefore, this study found that the newly synthesised thiosemicarbazones PPP4MT and PPP4PyrT and their corresponding gold(III) complexes $[\text{Au}(\text{PPP4MT})\text{Cl}]^+$ and $[\text{Au}(\text{PPP4PyrT})\text{Cl}]^+$ have potent antiproliferative activity against breast cancer cells, although coordination to gold(III) resulted in reduced efficacy compared to the free ligands. According to the IC_{50} values, PPP4MT is the most potent compound, and the new compounds demonstrated a clear structure–activity relationship; pyrrolidine-substituted gold complex proved to be the weakest of the four studied agents. In accordance with Lipinski's Rule of Five, results suggest that the lipophilicity and molecular weight of these compounds are critical to determining their antiproliferative activity, since they influence the ability of the compounds to permeate the cell membrane and thereby reach the intended intracellular targets. The molecular structure of these compounds, specifically their steric bulk at the N4-terminus and kinetic inertness of the gold centre, were additional factors found to contribute to the overall potency of these thiosemicarbazones. Therefore, this study demonstrates and confirms the large influence that metal coordination and functional group modification has on efficacy of certain therapeutic drugs; ultimately, this demonstrates that more research and further work is required to optimise the balance between stability and lability of novel gold-based metallodrugs.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Author
Jason Liu – Griffith University.
jason.liu@griffithuni.edu.au

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■ ABBREVIATIONS

A570, absorbance at 570 nm; Au(III), gold(III); AuPPP4MTCl, Au(III) complex of PPP4MT (chlorido complex); AuPPP4PyrTCl, Au(III) complex of PPP4PyrT (chlorido complex); CO₂, carbon dioxide; CTR1, copper transporter 1; DMSO, dimethyl sulfoxide; EDTA, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid; EGFR, epidermal growth factor receptor; ER, estrogen receptor; FCS, foetal calf serum; G1/S, cell-cycle checkpoint between G1 and S phase; H₂O₂, hydrogen peroxide; HBA, hydrogen-bond acceptors; HBD, hydrogen-bond donors; HER2, human epidermal growth factor receptor 2; IC₅₀, half-maximal inhibitory concentration; LMP, lysosomal membrane permeabilisation; logP (calc), calculated partition coefficient; MEM, minimum essential medium; MDR, multidrug resistance; MTT, 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide; NDRG1, N-myc downstream-regulated gene 1; PBS, phosphate-buffered saline; PI3K, phosphatidylinositol-3-kinase; PR, progesterone receptor; Pt(II), platinum(II); PPP4MT, PPP phenyl-pyridine thiosemicarbazone ligand (methyl-substituted); PPP4PyrT, PPP phenyl-pyridine thiosemicarbazone ligand (pyrrolidine-substituted); ROS, reactive oxygen species; RR, ribonucleotide reductase; SAR, structure-activity relationship(s); SD, standard deviation; TfR1, transferrin receptor 1; TNBC, triple-negative breast cancer; TPSA, topological polar surface area; TrxR, thioredoxin reductase.

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